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THE PROBLEMS OF THE MODERN YOUTH AND THE REAL WORLD IN “LOOKING FOR ALASKA” BY JOHN GREEN

Abstract

J. Green's novel "Looking for Alaska" opens in the context of a young man's views on life and sheds light on certain problems. It turns out that modern youth living anywhere in the world faces the same issues. In this regard, the author of the thesis connects the real world and the problem of youth with the inner world of the hero and notes that it stems from his internal contradictions and struggle with himself. Thus, the real world has its own laws and difficult-to-solve problems. The young hero can't restore himself and his identity unless he comes to terms with them. For this, education, family and friends play a major role. J. Green sees the problems that young people face when they are not heard and encourages them to listen throughout the novel. This makes it clear that they also have something to say.

Keywords: John Green, "Looking for Alaska", Novel, Real World, Modern Youth

1. Introduction

The modern American writer John Green (1977) is a writer who writes about the problems of the younger generation, called the "voice of youth" (Tamaki, 2019). J. Green not only speaks the language of modern youth, but also writes about what they want, what they want to express. In this regard, J. Green is compared to the powerful novelist of American prose, Jerome Sellanger. The hero of Jerome Sellanger's novel "The Catcher in the Rye" also speaks in the voice of the younger generation. Using the language of the teenager Holden Caulfield, the author speaks about the America of his time, and expresses his opinion on the processes taking place around the world in a broader sense. The work openly criticizes the American realities of the 20th century. What is interesting is that the author puts all this forward in the language of a sixteen-year-old teenager. In this regard, J. Green continues the narrative type of J. Selenger, presenting the teenager's outlook on life, his suffering and pain, along with the problem of alienation, through the language of the hero.

The hero of the novel "Looking for Alaska" (2005), a sixteen-year-old young man, Miles Halter, loses contact with his parents, can't communicate either at school or at home, seeks adventure and decides to study at a new school. Spending all his time on social networks and at the computer, Miles wants to get out of the closed circle he has fallen into. However, in the new school he meets young people who also experience his problems. Young boys deprived of parental love act in groups, while those who are left out of the group are isolated, and sometimes beaten. Miles's parents are so absorbed in their work that they do not suspect the absence of his friend or classmate. They are generally distant from Miles's thoughts and desires and don't see his associative development. They don't even notice the absence of their classmates at the party organized to celebrate Miles's move from Florida to Alabama, to a new school. They hold the party as a parental duty. American critic Daniel Feinberg, who extensively analyzed the work, wrote that Miles's loneliness stems from his desire to escape, to find new friends in new

circumstances, to continue his new life, but he unknowingly leads him to new uncertainty (Fienberg, 2019).

It should be noted that many teenagers and young people saw themselves in Miles's thoughts, especially in his outlook on life. This is understandable and comprehensible because it is precisely at this age that young people are in search of their identity. We would even say that many of them experience an identity crisis, sometimes withdraw into loneliness, and isolate themselves from society. J. Green's novel is interesting in this respect because young people of this age should know that they are not alone. The reasons for their loneliness and sometimes alienation come first from the family, and then from society.

On the other hand, J. Green's novel "Looking for Alaska" helps parents get to know their children better and see what difficulties they face when their dream world, the world of adolescence, encounters the real world, which is not always fair. From this point of view, J. Green describes the real world, shows the unwritten laws that prevail in society as they are. He also shows that misunderstandings also occur among young people, and in their world, there is a real situation that adults face. There are ways that lead to the loneliness of young people, to their complete withdrawal into themselves. That is why young people should be given the chance to be themselves, to live according to their will and desires.

2. The problem of alienation in the novel "Looking for Alaska"

Sixteen-year-old Miles wants to be himself, to start his life from scratch. Interestingly, the story is told in the first person and in the past tense, and thus, he recalls what happened to him: "The week before I left my family and Florida and the rest of my minor life to go to boarding school in Alabama, my mother insisted on throwing me a going-away party. To say that I had low expectations would be to underestimate the matter dramatically. Although I was more or less forced to invite all my "school friends," ... I knew they wouldn't come". (Green, 2006: 5).

J. Green tells his story in the language of a young man, but the attentive reader sees himself and at the same time the young man he meets in his everyday life. The writer builds the narrative in such a way that the events do not proceed sequentially. First, Miles talks about his new school, and then about the time he lived with his parents, then about his early school years. Then he talks about the death of Alaska, with whom he had just become friends. And gradually returning to the present day (Before one hundred thirty-six days before - the first chapter of the work begins with this title), the reader learns about Alaska and her story. This is reminiscent of the narrative line of postmodern novels (Abdullayeva, 2021: 24). The reader encounters non-standard judgments in Miles's worldview and it becomes clear that he does not want to be like everyone else. In order to be like everyone else, he also thinks differently, likening himself to intellectuals, a former statesman, a writer and a powerful commander. In this regard, he scares first his parents, and then his new friends.

Miles's favorite pastime is collecting aphorisms of great personalities. One of the last aphorisms is the phrase "I go to seek a Great Perhaps" used by the French writer Rabelais before his death: "Francois Rabelais. He was this poet. And his last words were 'I go to seek a Great Perhaps.' That's why I'm going. So, I don't have to wait until I die to start seeking a Great Perhaps". But he also thinks: And that quieted them. I was after a Great Perhaps, and they knew as well as I did that I wasn't going to find it ..." (Green, 2006: 17).

Miles goes after the great "Perhaps", but unknowingly falls into the trap of his other favorite aphorism. The leader of the struggle for the independence of the Spanish colonies in America, the political figure Simon Bolivar, asked "How will I ever get out of this labyrinth?" The phrase becomes the question of his life.

The work is very clearly about the acute understanding of American realities by a sixteen-year-old young man named Miles and the consequences of the general rules and morals of modern society (Ferguson, 2019). The labyrinth in which modern youth, who are "withdrawn to themselves" and "alone" with their own existence, fall into is the problem of youth living anywhere in the world. Apparently, this is why the novel "Looking for Alaska" is very popular among young people and is translated into many languages of the world.

The young hero of the novel also leaves the school he is studying at in order to confirm his sense of self-confidence and identity and goes to a school in another city, far from his home. In this school, he encounters real life and is forced to make a choice. Going through lies, deceit and betrayal, he realizes the value of true friendship, finds himself and his identity. He meets his first love; a girl named Alaska, and loses her almost immediately. J. Green raises serious questions about life and death and makes us think. Alaska's death, not as a result of suicide, but in an accidental car accident, opens up the topic of reconsidering the most important values, thinking about existence and death, and making life meaningful. J. Green calls on us not to forget that we are human even in the most difficult moments of life, and to make the right choice. It should be noted

that the writer seems to be entering into a polemic with the work of the Austrian psychologist Viktor Frankl, "Man's Search for Meaning". It is known that according to V. Frankl's psychological method, it is possible to find meaning in all moments of life, even in the most terrible moments, and thereby create an incentive to continue living (Frankl, 1984: 26).

The young hero of the novel can't escape the closed circle created by social and domestic problems and overcome the problems he has taken on. His outlook on life is confused, he experiences an identity crisis and raises numerous questions about himself and his surroundings. Miles suffers from a feeling of "uselessness" and loneliness, and is left alone with the fear of losing himself and his identity. At the same time, he is completely left to his own devices in his family. It is in this situation that he comes up with the idea of adding new meaning to his life and making it meaningful. Miles goes to a new school, in pursuit of a new life, to add meaning to his life.

He suffers from misunderstanding in the first days at school. According to the American psychologist Abraham Maslow, when parents fail to provide a safe, appropriate and suitable environment, children develop feelings of distrust along with deep feelings of insecurity. A. Maslow believes that feelings of comfort and peace lead people to freely express their inner potential (Maslow, 1998: 31). Miles also seeks comfort and peace in a new school, but can't find it in the first days. Gradually, as he gains like-minded people and friends, he regains his sense of self-confidence, has certain goals for life, and looks to the future with confidence. Each of his friends teaches Miles a life lesson with his stories. Throughout the novel, Miles lives an internally tense life, embodying the hero whose spiritual and moral searches take him from adolescence to youth. Throughout the work, the reader sees his character undergo certain changes, witnesses the painful searches for his identity and personality. The search for identity and freedom leads him to continue living without fear, to restore his personality.

A. Maslow writes in his work "Motivation and Personality" about the importance of a person's sense of self-affirmation and self-confidence and personal relationships and notes that people need social love and human connection, a self-actualized person satisfies these needs and is able to follow his own path (Maslow, 1998: 92). Miles also finds Alaska, loves her, her individual characteristics attract Miles to himself, help him understand and comprehend life. Both of them talk about yesterday and today, share their thoughts and ideas about the future. The friendship, which lasted until Alaska's accidental death in an accident, takes on a new meaning after Alaska's death. Thus, J. Green penetrates the spiritual world of a teenager, shows his psychological age with the characteristics typical of a teenager, emphasizes the problems he faces as a social problem of society. But at the same time, the hero's evolution, his departure from the world of dreams, his losses and gains are presented as part of life. The work ends with Miles's thoughts about life and death, youth and maturity. The young man sums up the trials he has gone through and thus says goodbye to his teenage

years. But one thing is indisputable for him: “We cannot be born, and we cannot die. Like all energy, we can only change shapes and sizes and manifestations. They forget that when they get old. They get scared of losing and failing. But that part of us greater than the sum of our parts cannot begin and cannot end, and so it cannot fail” (Green, 2006: 27).

It is known that many young people are faced with the question of whether to accept the current situation and go with the flow, or change everything and live only as they want. According to the American psychologist Erik Erikson, the author of the concept of “identity crisis”, the essence of identity is defined as an unexpectedly arising sense of personal identity, the integrity of the individual. However, this concept is considered not only personal, but also group (Ericson, 1998: 105). Miles is experiencing an identity crisis, looking for his own path and, going through the process of self-awareness, finally gaining independence. But before that, he has to go through certain paths, restore his identity and self-confidence. Life teaches him that sometimes a person’s happiness is in very small things. He should just live and love the present, appreciate every minute, and not save life for the future.

Miles’s identity crisis makes him lonely, he thinks that he can’t find his place. So, he does not like what his environment offers him. It seems to him that everyone is against him. Alaska and her friends are treated with suspicion in the first few days. He is not like the young people of his age who strive for comfort and social status. It is extremely difficult for him to find a common language with such young people: “...and then you’ve got the Weekday Warriors; they board here, but they’re all rich kids who live in Birmingham and go home to their parents’ air-conditioned mansions every weekend” (Green, 2006: 34). Miles does not understand this type of children and never feels comfortable around them. The “rich kids” do not like Miles from the first day; they make fun of him and put him in a funny situation at any time. Alaska, on the other hand, resents him, demanding that he not bow down to the “rich kids”, to be planned towards them and to respond in this way. John Green’s peculiarity as a writer is that he creates a sharp contrast between Alaska and Miles, preserving the individuality of the former, and emphasizing the desire of the latter to be accepted. Despite all the difficulties and the loss of her spiritual ties, Alaska manages to find strength and stand on her feet. Even in moments when she can’t, she “flits” and looks for ways to protect herself from “rich kids” possessing parents who mentally crush everyone (Green, 2006: 34). Alaska repeatedly advises him to be brave and overcome his fear. Miles makes her look at Bolivar’s labyrinth from a different perspective: “You spend your whole life stuck in the labyrinth, thinking about how you’ll escape it one day, and how awesome it will be, and imagining that the future keeps you going, but you never do it. You just use the future to escape the present” (Green, 2006: 41).

Miles is distinguished by his self-contained, distant and “sinful” personality until he meets her.

Alaska’s death restores Miles’ identity, self-confidence, he finds himself, his individuality, and realizes the “Big Maybe”.

Miles is not a young man who can fit into standard molds; he is overly sensitive and gets excited at times, his emotional state betrays him. His silence, his lack of fighting spirit like Alaska, is clearly connected with his incompatibility with society. This alienates him from society, from the society in which he lives. True, he also wants freedom, liberty, but he seems to be “surplus” in a false system with certain values. He feels lonely in such a system of values created by society. Apparently, that is why the most important thing for him is, as he himself says, “The nature of the labyrinth, I scribbled into my spiral notebook, and the way out of it” (Green, 2006: 59).

Miles, who is as innocent and pure as a child, is in search of truth. This indicates his romantic mood and maximalism. It is no coincidence that Miles chooses Simon Bolivar’s thought “How will I ever get out of this labyrinth!” as his motto. It seems to him that if Bolivar was able to get out of the labyrinths of life, then he will definitely find a way out. It is worth noting here that Miles’s maximalism is based on the fact that he relies not on ordinary people, but on outstanding personalities who have left their mark on history. But someone who thinks so broadly gets lost in life situations, in the worries of everyday life, and can’t get out of its labyrinths. Apparently, this is why he is prone to loneliness, and after the death of Alaska, he defines for himself: “Thomas Edison’s last words were: “It’s very beautiful over there.” I don’t know where there is, but I believe it’s somewhere, and I hope it’s beautiful”.

3. Conclusion

J. Green’s Miles is somewhere between a teenager who understands reality and a young man stuck in illusions. Undoubtedly, he is going through a period of transition, but at the same time he consciously does not like the world of adults and does not want to participate in it. The reader sees the events of both him and his school friends, especially Alaska, through Miles’ eyes and therefore can’t make any further judgments. He can’t say for sure whether what Miles says is fiction or truth. However, he is absolutely sure that what Miles narrates is similar to the life story of a young man living anywhere in the world. Miles’s loneliness, alienation from everyone and the search for his own identity are a reflection of his inner turmoil and struggle with himself. The criticism of society voiced by his tongue, his sincerity and naivety also stem from the contradictions of a cruel and hypocritical world. Therefore, the search for ideals becomes his life credo, Rabelais. Bolivar, Edison seem to be values on which he can rely. Thus, he searches for purity and truth in the world, and when he cannot find it, he becomes lonely and withdrawn. His relationship with his schoolmates emphasizes his loneliness and, at the same time, his incomprehensibility. The conclusion that Miles comes to at the end also raises questions, and although his thoughts bring some clarity to the work, many questions remain open.

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